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**Comparative Analysis of Topology-Aware
Pathfinding:
Evaluating Persistent Homology Against
Traditional Heuristic
Methods**

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of Computer Science**

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Abstract

Pathfinding in complex topological spaces presents unique challenges, particularly when traditional heuristics fail to account for underlying topological constraints. This work investigates the application of **topological data analysis (TDA)**, specifically **persistent homology (PH)** computed from **Vietoris–Rips complexes (VR complexes)**, to enhance classical pathfinding algorithms such as **A***, **Weighted A***, and **Greedy Best-First Search**. Theoretical chapters provide a foundation in graph-based search methods, simplicial complexes, homology, and the principles of PH, establishing a framework for integrating topological information into heuristic design. Experimentally, synthetic **point clouds** representing surfaces with nontrivial topology — including spheres, tori, Klein bottles, and crosscaps — are used to construct **k-nearest neighbor graphs**. Persistent 1-dimensional cycles (H1) extracted from these VR complexes inform heuristic penalties, guiding search algorithms around topological obstacles. Experiments explore the effects of point cloud density, start and goal selection, and algorithmic parameters, demonstrating the influence of topological features on path selection, connectivity, and computational efficiency. The work highlights how combining theoretical insights from algebraic topology with practical search methods can lead to more robust navigation strategies on complex surfaces.

Contents

1	Introduction	2
2	Traditional Heuristic Pathfinding Methods	4
2.1	Graph Fundamentals for Pathfinding	4
2.2	Dijkstra	7
2.3	Uniform Cost Search	10
2.4	Heuristics	13
2.5	A* Algorithm	14
2.6	Weighted A*	17
2.7	Greedy Best-First Search	18
3	Topology-Aware Pathfinding	20
3.1	Topology and TDA	20
3.2	Simplicial complexes	22
3.3	Homology	24
3.4	Persistent Homology	28
3.5	Integrating PH into Pathfinding	31
4	Comparative Analysis	34
4.1	Experimental Setup	34
4.1.1	Datasets	34
4.1.2	Graph and Complex Construction	38
4.1.3	Evaluation Goals	39
4.1.4	Tools and Implementation	39
4.1.5	Experimental Parameters	40
4.1.6	Results	41
5	Conclusion	45

Chapter 1

Introduction

Pathfinding Overview

Pathfinding (also referred to as pathing or wayfinding) is the process of computing an efficient route between two points within a given environment. This task is usually performed by computer applications operating on a structured representation of the environment, most commonly a graph or a grid. The problem extends beyond simply finding the shortest distance: in many real-world scenarios, additional requirements arise, such as obstacle avoidance, optimality under varying cost functions, adaptability to dynamic environments, or robustness under uncertainty.

Applications of pathfinding are widespread, spanning across domains such as robotics (autonomous navigation), mapping and geographic information systems (GIS), video games (character movement and strategy planning), logistics and supply chain management, computer networks, and unmanned aerial vehicles (drones).

Role of Graph Theory

Graph theory provides a powerful abstraction for pathfinding problems by allowing environments of diverse geometries to be expressed as nodes (states, positions, or points of interest) connected by edges (possible transitions or movements). This abstraction enables the application of classical graph algorithms. A foundational method is Dijkstra's algorithm, which guarantees optimality in computing the shortest path on weighted graphs.

When computational efficiency is critical, especially in large-scale or real-time systems, heuristic search algorithms such as A* are widely used. A* integrates a heuristic function into the search process, guiding the exploration of the graph to accelerate pathfinding while maintaining optimality under admissible heuristics. Variants such as Weighted A*, Greedy Best-First Search, and Jump Point Search have been introduced to further trade off between accuracy and speed.

Beyond Classical Heuristics

Despite their success, classical heuristics may become insufficient when dealing with environments of high complexity or non-Euclidean structure (e.g., surfaces with topological features such as holes, tunnels, or nontrivial connectivity). In such cases, enhancements are necessary:

Hierarchical approaches: Decomposing large environments into smaller subgraphs or regions to accelerate global search.

Probabilistic methods: Algorithms such as Probabilistic Roadmaps (PRM) and Rapidly-Exploring Random Trees (RRT) are effective in continuous or high-dimensional spaces.

Learning-based methods: Machine learning and reinforcement learning can adapt heuristics or policies to specific environments, improving performance in dynamic or partially known settings.

Topology-aware methods: Tools from algebraic topology (e.g., homology or persistent homology) can capture higher-level structures of the environment, helping algorithms avoid redundant exploration and respect global constraints.

Multi-objective optimization: In real-world tasks, optimality may involve trade-offs between distance, time, energy consumption, or safety margins.

Towards Topology-Aware Pathfinding

While traditional heuristic methods such as A^* and its variants perform well in many practical settings, their performance and correctness strongly depend on the assumption that the underlying environment can be adequately modeled as a simple Euclidean space or a regular grid. However, non-standard topological surfaces (such as the sphere, torus, crosscap, or Klein bottle) introduce challenges that classical heuristics may not capture effectively. On such spaces, notions of “closeness” or “shortest distance” are influenced by global connectivity and topological features that heuristics alone often overlook.

To address this, topology-aware approaches have recently emerged, offering tools to analyze and exploit the intrinsic structure of data. In particular, persistent homology, a method from algebraic topology, provides a way to extract and quantify topological features across scales. By representing data as shapes and studying their homological properties, it becomes possible to reason about obstacles, loops, voids, and connectivity patterns in a way that is invariant to noise and geometry.

The aim of this thesis is to explore the integration of persistent homology into pathfinding on complex surfaces, comparing it with traditional heuristic methods. The focus is on environments modeled not by ordinary grids or flat graphs, but by nontrivial topological spaces such as the sphere, torus, crosscap, and Klein bottle. These spaces serve as testbeds for evaluating how topological insights can enhance or complement classical approaches.

Ultimately, the motivation lies in the fact that modern data is often high-dimensional, irregular, and structured in complex ways. Viewing data through a topological lens and presenting it in the form of a shape may open new directions for pathfinding and optimization tasks, where traditional heuristics struggle or fail to scale.

Chapter 2

Traditional Heuristic Pathfinding Methods

2.1 Graph Fundamentals for Pathfinding

All pathfinding methods operate on data that represent the environment in some way. These can be graphs, weighted graphs, grids (or occupancy maps), point clouds, etc. In this thesis, the explanations involve weighted, directed graph-based representations, since they are widely used in pathfinding research and provide a flexible image for a variety of environments. Also, the graphs we will work with are *finite*, meaning that $|V| < \infty$ and $|E| < \infty$. Finite graphs are considered because infinite graphs are uncommon in computational pathfinding and are impractical to store explicitly.

To formally describe these concepts, we first define graphs, directed graphs, and weighted graphs.

Definition 2.1. A **graph** is a pair $G = (V, E)$, where V is a set whose elements are called **vertices** (or nodes), and E is a set of pairs (v_1, v_2) of vertices, whose elements are called **edges** (sometimes **links** or **lines**).

Definition 2.2. A **directed graph**, also called a **digraph**, is a graph in which the E is a set of directed pairs (v_1, v_2)

Definition 2.3. A **weighted** directed graph is a directed graph in which

$$\forall e \in E \exists w(e) \in \mathbb{R}.$$

We call $w(e)$ the **weight** (or **cost**) of the edge e . Weights can represent distance, time, cost, danger, or any metric relevant to the application.

To measure distances and search for a path it is needed to define these concepts.

Definition 2.4. Let $e = (u, v)$ be an edge with endpoints $u, v \in V$. We define the **distance** between u and v as

$$d(u, v) := w(e),$$

where $w(e)$ denotes the weight of the edge e .

Definition 2.5. Given a graph $G = (V, E)$ and $u, v \in V$, a **path** P between u and v is an ordered list of N edges of the form

$$P = \{(u, v_1), (v_1, v_2), \dots, (v_{N-2}, v_{N-1}), (v_{N-1}, v)\}.$$

Note that paths are not unique; there may exist multiple distinct paths between two nodes.

Definition 2.6. Let $P = (v_0, v_1, \dots, v_k)$ be a path in a weighted graph $G = (V, E)$, where each edge $(v_{i-1}, v_i) \in E$ has an associated weight $w(v_{i-1}, v_i) > 0$. The **distance** of the path P is defined as

$$d(P) = \sum_{i=1}^k w(v_{i-1}, v_i).$$

Furthermore, if P is a path between u and v , we equivalently write

$$d_P(u, v) = d(P).$$

However, it is necessary for algorithms to look for the optimal path.[1]

Definition 2.7. Let $\chi(u, v)$ be the set of all paths between two nodes u and v . A path $P \in \chi(u, v)$ is said to be **optimal** if and only if

$$d(P) \leq d(P') \quad \forall P' \in \chi(u, v).$$

where $d(P)$ is

Definition 2.8. Two nodes $u, v \in V$ are said to be **connected** if and only if there exists a path P between u and v .

The two most common structures for storing graphs are adjacency list and adjacency matrix.

Definition 2.9. An **adjacency list** is a data structure used to represent a graph where each node in the graph stores a list of its neighboring vertices.

Definition 2.10. An **adjacency matrix** a square matrix used to represent a finite graph. The elements of the matrix indicate whether pairs of vertices are adjacent or not in the graph.

Figure 2.1: Simple directed graph example

Adjacency List Representation

For the graph in Figure 2.1, the adjacency list is:

- A: B, D
- B: C
- C: A
- D: C

Adjacency Matrix Representation

The same graph can be represented as an adjacency matrix, where rows and columns correspond to vertices (A, B, C, D). A value of 1 indicates the presence of a directed edge.

	A	B	C	D
A	0	1	0	1
B	0	0	1	0
C	1	0	0	0
D	0	0	1	0

For the weighted graph representations differ a little.

Figure 2.2: Weighted graph example

Adjacency List Representation

For the weighted graph in Figure 2.2 , the adjacency list is:

A: B(5), D(6)
B: C(4)
C: A(5)
D: C(3)

Adjacency Matrix Representation

The same weighted graph can be represented as an adjacency matrix, where rows and columns correspond to vertices (A, B, C, D). The entry in row i and column j stores the weight of the directed edge from i to j (or 0 if no edge exists).

	A	B	C	D
A	0	5	0	6
B	0	0	4	0
C	5	0	0	0
D	0	0	3	0

And to compare these methods based on operation the Table 2.1 is described.

Comparison of Representations

Operation	Adjacency Matrix	Adjacency List
Memory usage	$O(V^2)$	$O(V + E)$
Check if edge exists	$O(1)$	$O(\deg(v))$
Iterate over neighbors	$O(V)$	$O(\deg(v))$
Best suited for	Dense graphs	Sparse graphs

Table 2.1: Comparison of adjacency matrix and adjacency list representations.

2.2 Dijkstra

Before introducing heuristic algorithms, it is essential to first examine Dijkstra's algorithm, which serves as the foundation for many shortest path methods.

To illustrate its workings, let us consider an example where we determine the shortest path from A to B .

Figure 2.3: Initial graph

Starting from node A , all nodes are initially labeled with ∞ , representing an unknown distance. The starting node is an exception and is labeled with 0. Additionally, a queue of vertices to be explored is maintained. At the beginning:

$$Q = \{A\}.$$

Figure 2.4: Labeling distances

Dijkstra's algorithm repeats the following process:

1. Update distance estimates for neighbors of the current vertex.

2. Select the unexplored vertex with the smallest estimate.
3. Append this vertex to the queue.

Following this process, nodes C and F are updated.

Figure 2.5: Updating estimates for C and F

The next unexplored vertex with the smallest estimate is chosen, so the queue becomes

$$Q = \{A, F\}.$$

Figure 2.6: Label F as explored

The process continues. Node C is not updated, since the newly calculated distance (4) is greater than its current label (3). Thus, the queue evolves to

$$Q = \{A, F, C\}.$$

Figure 2.7: C is explored

Figure 2.8: Explore E

The queue is now

$$Q = \{A, F, C, E\}.$$

Figure 2.9: The goal B is reached

Finally, the algorithm reaches the goal. The shortest path is

$$A \rightarrow F \rightarrow C \rightarrow B,$$

with a total length of 6. The pseudocode is described in Algorithm 1

Algorithm 1 Dijkstra's Algorithm

Require: Graph $G = (V, E)$, edge weights $w(e) > 0$, source node $s \in V$

Ensure: Shortest path estimates $d[v]$ for all $v \in V$

```
1: for all vertices  $v \in V$  do
2:    $d[v] \leftarrow \infty$ 
3:    $\text{prev}[v] \leftarrow \text{undefined}$ 
4: end for
5:  $d[s] \leftarrow 0$ 
6:  $Q \leftarrow V$  {priority queue with keys  $d[v]$ }
7: while  $Q \neq \emptyset$  do
8:    $u \leftarrow \text{Extract-Min}(Q)$ 
9:   for all neighbors  $v$  of  $u$  do
10:    if  $d[v] > d[u] + w(u, v)$  then
11:       $d[v] \leftarrow d[u] + w(u, v)$ 
12:       $\text{prev}[v] \leftarrow u$ 
13:       $\text{Decrease-Key}(Q, v, d[v])$ 
14:    end if
15:  end for
16: end while
```

2.3 Uniform Cost Search

Uniform Cost Search (UCS) can be viewed as a special case of Dijkstra's algorithm. While Dijkstra's method computes the shortest paths to all vertices, UCS is applied in search problems where the goal may not be known in advance. The algorithm proceeds by expanding the path with the lowest cost so far, and it terminates as soon as a goal node is reached. Unlike heuristic algorithms such as A*, UCS relies solely on accumulated path costs, without using additional estimates.[2]

Let us examine its behavior on an example where S is the start node, and $G1, G2, G3$ are goal nodes.

Figure 2.10: Initial graph

We will represent the explored states as a tree and maintain a list of nodes already visited. Firstly, S is explored. Since it is not a goal state, the tree is expanded.

Figure 2.11: Expand S

At this point, $\text{Visited}=\{S\}$. The cheapest path is from S to A , so it is expanded next.

Figure 2.12: Expand A

Now $\text{Visited}=\{S, A\}$. There are four active paths. The cheapest one leads to D with a total cost of 6. The node S can also be revisited from D , but since it has already been explored at a lower cost, it is not added again.

Figure 2.13: Expand D

Now $\text{Visited}=\{S, A, D\}$. There are five active paths, three of them with total cost 8. The algorithm continues with the leftmost node B . Since A is already in the visited list, it is not added again. Instead, new branches expand into C and E .

Figure 2.14: Expand B, C, E

There are now six active paths. The lowest cost is 9, corresponding to nodes B and C . However, since both were already reached earlier with smaller costs, they are treated as dead ends and not expanded further.

Figure 2.15: Dead ends for B and C

At this point, four active paths remain. The next one leads to $G2$ with a cost of 13. Since $G2$ is a goal state, the algorithm terminates here. The returned solution path is:

$$S \rightarrow D \rightarrow C \rightarrow G2,$$

and UCS guarantees that this path is optimal.

The pseudocode is described in Algorithm 2

Algorithm 2 Uniform Cost Search

Require: Graph $G = (V, E)$, edge costs $w(e) > 0$, start node s , set of goal nodes G^*

Ensure: Optimal path from s to some $g \in G^*$

```
1: Create a priority queue  $Q$  ordered by path cost
2: Insert  $(s, 0)$  into  $Q$  {node with cumulative cost}
3: Initialize an empty map  $\text{prev}[v]$  for predecessors
4: while  $Q \neq \emptyset$  do
5:    $(u, c) \leftarrow \text{Extract-Min}(Q)$ 
6:   if  $u \in G^*$  then
7:     return Reconstruct-Path( $\text{prev}, u$ ) {goal reached}
8:   end if
9:   for all neighbors  $v$  of  $u$  do
10:     $\text{newCost} \leftarrow c + w(u, v)$ 
11:    if  $v$  not in  $Q$  or  $\text{newCost} < \text{cost}(v)$  then
12:      Update  $\text{cost}(v) \leftarrow \text{newCost}$ 
13:       $\text{prev}[v] \leftarrow u$ 
14:      Insert or Decrease-Key( $Q, (v, \text{newCost})$ )
15:    end if
16:  end for
17: end while
18: return failure {no goal reachable} =0
```

2.4 Heuristics

Heuristics in computer science refers to a techniques for problem-solving including pathfinding algorithms. They are rules or strategies derived from prior knowledge or experience. The technique focuses on making the decision quickly rather than perfectly or optimally efficient. Therefore, it is applied when classical approaches are time consuming, as well as when an appropriate solution cannot be found with a classical approach.

Heuristic methods differ from non-heuristic ones in that they use a *heuristic function*. A heuristic function must satisfy certain conditions; it cannot be arbitrary. Thus, the formal definition is the following.[3][4]

Definition 2.11. A **heuristic function** is a mapping

$$h : S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$$

from the set of states S to the non-negative real numbers, such that $h(n)$ is an estimate of the cost of the cheapest path from state $n \in S$ to a goal state.

In order for the heuristic to result in an optimal path, the heuristic must be *admissible*. Formally, a heuristic function h is admissible if it never overestimates the true cost to the goal.

Definition 2.12. Let $h(s)$ be a heuristic estimate from state s to the goal, and let $c(s)$ be the optimal cost from s to the goal. The heuristic h is **admissible** if and only if

$$\forall s \in S, h(s) \leq c(s).$$

This means that the heuristic never predicts a cost greater than the actual cost of reaching the goal. However, admissibility alone does not ensure that a search algorithm is efficient. For instance, if it happens that

$$\forall s \in S : c(s) \geq 0$$

and

$$\forall s \in S : h(s) = 0,$$

then the priority of s is

$$f(s) = g(s) + h(s) = g(s) + 0 = g(s),$$

where $g(s)$ denotes cost from start to s , which is equivalent to uniform-cost search and does not provide any advantage to the pathfinding algorithm. Therefore, the heuristic has to be as large as possible while still remaining admissible.

While admissibility ensures that the solution is optimal, it does not guarantee efficiency. To address this, another desirable property is consistency (or monotonicity).[1][5]

Definition 2.13. A heuristic function h is **consistent** (or **monotonic**) if and only if:

1. $h(\text{goal}) = 0$,
2. $\forall s \in S, \forall n \in \text{neighbors}(s) : h(s) \leq c(s, n) + h(n)$,

where $c(s, n)$ is the step cost from s to n , and $\text{Neighbors}(s)$ is the set of all states reachable in one step from s .

Additionally, consistency implies admissibility, although the reverse is not necessarily true. The search in general will be more efficient if heuristic is consistent.

The examples of heuristic functions are:

- **Manhattan Distance:** Commonly used on grids with 4-directional movement (up, down, left, right). For two points (x_1, y_1) and (x_2, y_2) the heuristic is

$$h(s) = |x_1 - x_2| + |y_1 - y_2|.$$

- **Euclidean Distance:** Suitable when diagonal movement is allowed, or when movement cost is proportional to physical distance:

$$h(s) = \sqrt{(x_1 - x_2)^2 + (y_1 - y_2)^2}.$$

- **Chebyshev Distance:** Used in grids with 8-directional movement (like kings on a chessboard). The heuristic is:

$$h(s) = \max(|x_1 - x_2|, |y_1 - y_2|).$$

- **Domain-Specific Heuristics:** In robotics, heuristics may consider energy consumption or terrain difficulty. In games, heuristics can incorporate factors such as enemy positions or safe zones.

2.5 A* Algorithm

The A* algorithm is the most common choice for pathfinding and produces optimal solutions in many cases due to its use of a heuristic function, which makes it an *informed* search method in comparison with Uniform Cost Search (UCS). It guarantees to find a path if one exists (assuming a finite graph and non-negative edge weights). Additionally, the algorithm is flexible, as different heuristics can be applied to adapt it to diverse environments. Therefore, it is widely applicable.

Uniform Cost Search (UCS) assigns the priority of a state s as

$$f(s) = g(s),$$

where $g(s)$ is the total cost from the start node to s .

The A* algorithm enhances UCS by incorporating a heuristic estimate $h(s)$. Its priority function is

$$f(s) = g(s) + h(s),$$

where $h(s)$ is an admissible heuristic estimating the cost from s to the goal.

Supposing that a heuristic is already chosen and computed, the example graph from the previous chapter is now informed with *estimates*.

Figure 2.16: Initial graph with heuristic values

For node D and $G3$, the estimated value is 6, while the actual cost is 9. This happens to be an *underestimate*. Since the estimates never overestimate the true cost, the heuristic is admissible, and the algorithm computes the shortest path.

Expanding the start node S , we calculate priorities for its successors, obtaining $\text{Visited} = \{S(5)\}$.

Figure 2.17: Expand S and calculate priorities

The next steps proceed as in UCS, except that the priority is calculated as the sum of the total cost and the heuristic value. Expanding nodes A and B , we update the visited set:

$$\text{Visited} = \{S(5), A(12), B(11)\}.$$

Figure 2.18: Expand *A* and *B*

Next, nodes *D* and *C* are expanded, giving

$$\text{Visited} = \{S(5), A(12), B(11), D(12), C(12)\}.$$

Figure 2.19: Expand *D* and *C*

Finally, expanding *E* provides a path to the goal node.

Figure 2.20: Expand *E*

At this point, the goal node is reached, and the algorithm terminates.

$$\text{Visited} = \{S(5), A(12), B(11), D(12), C(12), E(13)\}$$

The shortest path is successfully found:

$$S \rightarrow D \rightarrow C \rightarrow G2.$$

This example illustrates how A* combines the exact cost $g(s)$ and the heuristic estimate $h(s)$ to guide the search more efficiently than UCS while still guaranteeing the optimal path when the heuristic is admissible. The pseudocode is presented in Algorithm 3.

Algorithm 3 A* Search Algorithm

```
1: Input: Graph  $G = (V, E)$ , start node  $s$ , goal node  $g$ , heuristic function  $h$ 
2: Output: Optimal path from  $s$  to  $g$  (if one exists)
3: Initialize open set  $O \leftarrow \{s\}$ 
4: Initialize closed set  $C \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
5: For all  $v \in V$ : set  $g(v) \leftarrow \infty$ ,  $f(v) \leftarrow \infty$ 
6: Set  $g(s) \leftarrow 0$ ,  $f(s) \leftarrow h(s)$ 
7: while  $O \neq \emptyset$  do
8:   Select  $n \in O$  with minimum  $f(n)$ 
9:   if  $n = g$  then
10:    Return reconstructed path from  $s$  to  $g$ 
11:   end if
12:   Move  $n$  from  $O$  to  $C$ 
13:   for each neighbor  $m$  of  $n$  do
14:     if  $m \in C$  then
15:       continue
16:     end if
17:     tentative_g  $\leftarrow g(n) + c(n, m)$ 
18:     if  $m \notin O$  then
19:       Add  $m$  to  $O$ 
20:     else if tentative_g  $\geq g(m)$  then
21:       continue
22:     end if
23:     Set parent of  $m \leftarrow n$ 
24:     Set  $g(m) \leftarrow$  tentative_g
25:     Set  $f(m) \leftarrow g(m) + h(m)$ 
26:   end for
27: end while
28: Return failure (no path exists) =0
```

2.6 Weighted A*

Weighted A* (WA*) is a modification of the standard A* algorithm in which the heuristic function h is inflated by a fixed factor $1 + \varepsilon$, where $\varepsilon > 0$. Consequently, the evaluation function is defined as

$$f^\uparrow(s) = g(s) + (1 + \varepsilon) \cdot h(s),$$

where $g(s)$ denotes the cost from the start node to the current node s , and $h(s)$ is the heuristic estimate of the cost from s to the goal.

Alternatively, the inflation factor is often expressed as a weight parameter $w \geq 1$, such that the evaluation function becomes

$$f(s) = g(s) + w \cdot h(s).$$

The introduction of $w > 1$ biases the search more strongly towards the heuristic, typically resulting in faster computation at the expense of optimality. Weighted A* is particularly advantageous in applications where computational efficiency is prioritized over strict optimality.[6]

The procedure is outlined in Algorithm 4.

Algorithm 4 Weighted A* Search Algorithm

```

1: Input: Graph  $G = (V, E)$ , start node  $s$ , goal node  $g$ , heuristic function  $h$ , weight  $w \geq 1$ 
2: Output: Path from  $s$  to  $g$  (may not be strictly optimal if  $w > 1$ )
3: Initialize open set  $O \leftarrow \{s\}$ 
4: Initialize closed set  $C \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
5: For all  $v \in V$ : set  $g(v) \leftarrow \infty$ ,  $f(v) \leftarrow \infty$ 
6: Set  $g(s) \leftarrow 0$ ,  $f(s) \leftarrow w \cdot h(s)$ 
7: while  $O \neq \emptyset$  do
8:   Select  $n \in O$  with minimum  $f(n)$ 
9:   if  $n = g$  then
10:    Return reconstructed path from  $s$  to  $g$ 
11:   end if
12:   Move  $n$  from  $O$  to  $C$ 
13:   for each neighbor  $m$  of  $n$  do
14:     if  $m \in C$  then
15:       continue
16:     end if
17:     tentative_g  $\leftarrow g(n) + c(n, m)$ 
18:     if  $m \notin O$  then
19:       Add  $m$  to  $O$ 
20:     else if tentative_g  $\geq g(m)$  then
21:       continue
22:     end if
23:     Set parent of  $m \leftarrow n$ 
24:     Set  $g(m) \leftarrow$  tentative_g
25:     Set  $f(m) \leftarrow g(m) + w \cdot h(m)$ 
26:   end for
27: end while
28: Return failure (no path exists) =0

```

2.7 Greedy Best-First Search

Greedy Best-First Search (GBFS) is a heuristic-driven pathfinding algorithm that expands nodes based solely on their heuristic estimate of the cost to the goal, while ignoring the cost already incurred. The evaluation function is therefore defined as

$$f(s) = h(s),$$

where $h(s)$ is the heuristic estimate of the distance from node s to the goal. Unlike A* and its variants, GBFS does not guarantee optimality or completeness in general, but it is often significantly faster due to its strong bias towards the goal.

The procedure is presented in Algorithm 5.

Algorithm 5 Greedy Best-First Search Algorithm

```
1: Input: Graph  $G = (V, E)$ , start node  $s$ , goal node  $g$ , heuristic function  $h$ 
2: Output: Path from  $s$  to  $g$  (not guaranteed optimal)
3: Initialize open set  $O \leftarrow \{s\}$ 
4: Initialize closed set  $C \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
5: For all  $v \in V$ : set parent  $\pi(v) \leftarrow \text{null}$ 
6: For all  $v \in V$ : set  $f(v) \leftarrow h(v)$ 
7: while  $O \neq \emptyset$  do
8:   Select  $n \in O$  with minimum  $f(n)$ 
9:   if  $n = g$  then
10:    return Reconstructed path from  $s$  to  $g$  using  $\pi$ 
11:   end if
12:   Move  $n$  from  $O$  to  $C$ 
13:   for each neighbor  $m$  of  $n$  do
14:     if  $m \in C$  then
15:       continue
16:     end if
17:     if  $m \notin O$  then
18:       Add  $m$  to  $O$ 
19:       Set parent of  $m \leftarrow n$ 
20:     end if
21:   end for
22: end while
23: Return failure (no path exists) =0
```

Chapter 3

Topology-Aware Pathfinding

3.1 Topology and TDA

Topology is a study of a shape. It is considered to be the way to define which points are near without specifying how near they are. For instance, objects, which are depicted on Figure 3.1 are topologically equivalent, since the first one can be deformed in the second one without puncturing or contracting any holes.

Figure 3.1: Cow and sphere.[7]

A formal definition for a topological space is the following.[8]

Definition 3.1. A **topology** on a point set X is a collection \mathcal{U} of subsets of X , called *open sets*, such that:

1. $X \in \mathcal{U}$ and $\emptyset \in \mathcal{U}$;
2. if $U_1, U_2 \in \mathcal{U}$, then $U_1 \cap U_2 \in \mathcal{U}$;
3. if $U_i \in \mathcal{U}$ for all i in some possibly infinite or uncountable index set, then $\bigcup_i U_i \in \mathcal{U}$.

The pair (X, \mathcal{U}) is called a **topological space**.

Algebraic topology offers a set of tools for counting and collating holes. Much of the research focuses on developing and fine-tuning *topological invariants*, which are numbers assigned to a shape. These invariants provide information about the global structure of the space. For instance, one important invariant is the Euler characteristic, defined as

$$\chi = V - E + F,$$

where V is the number of vertices, E the number of edges, and F the number of faces. For convex polyhedra, the Euler characteristic satisfies

$$\chi = 2.$$

See Figure 3.2

Name	Image	Vertices V	Edges E	Faces F	Euler characteristic: $\chi = V - E + F$
Tetrahedron		4	6	4	2
Hexahedron or cube		8	12	6	2
Octahedron		6	12	8	2
Dodecahedron		20	30	12	2
Icosahedron		12	30	20	2

Figure 3.2: Euler characteristic example for polyhedra.[9]

It was originally invented for polyhedra (see [10]), but can be computed for arbitrary surface by polygonization, see Figure 3.3.

<i>Cube</i>	<i>Sphere</i>	<i>Euler Characteristic</i>
	2	
<i>Cube with 1 cavity</i>	<i>Torus</i>	
	0	
<i>Cube with 2 cavities</i>	<i>Bitorus</i>	
	-2	

Figure 3.3: Euler characteristic example.[11]

Another topological invariant are *Betti numbers*. They form a sequence of integers that indicate how many holes of each dimension a topological space has. For instance, β_0 counts connected components, β_1 counts one-dimensional loops or tunnels, and β_2 counts enclosed voids. Betti numbers are also related to the *Euler characteristic* χ of a space, through the formula

$$\chi = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (-1)^i \beta_i,$$

which connects combinatorial topology with algebraic invariants. See Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4: Betti numbers example.[12]

Topological Data Analysis is a subfield of mathematics, also computational topology which has an application in computer science. The main idea lies in presenting the data as a shape. Nowadays, data volumes rapidly increases and it causes related issues. The real world data is frequently noisy and high-dimensional. The following Figure 3.5 shows the steps on how the data is translated into shape and then processed.[13]

Figure 3.5: TDA pipeline.[13]

3.2 Simplicial complexes

There are many ways to represent a topological space as a decomposition into simple pieces. This decomposition is called a *complex* if the pieces are topologically simple and their intersections are lower-dimensional pieces of the same type. Thus, the notion of a simplex must be defined.

A simplex is a generalization of a triangle to arbitrary dimensions. A 0-simplex is a single vertex, a 1-simplex is two vertices connected by an edge, a 2-simplex is three vertices connected pairwise by edges with a single face (or a triangle), a 3-simplex is four vertices connected pairwise by edges, joined by four faces which are filled in to form a tetrahedron.[14][15] Figure 3.6 illustrates 0- to 3-simplices in geometric form.

Figure 3.6: Simplicies example.[16]

A 4-simplex has five vertices, with edges, triangular faces, and tetrahedral cells forming a four-dimensional solid. An n -simplex is formed by $n+1$ vertices and the space between them, known as the convex hull of these vertices.

The formal representation involves a linear combination of vectors with coefficients.[17] For instance, the one-dimensional simplex may be written as

$$(1 - \lambda)\vec{v}_1 + \lambda\vec{v}_2, \quad \lambda \in [0, 1],$$

where \vec{v}_1 and \vec{v}_2 are vertices represented by vectors. Similarly, a two-dimensional simplex, which corresponds to a triangle, can be expressed as

$$\lambda_1\vec{v}_1 + \lambda_2\vec{v}_2 + \lambda_3\vec{v}_3, \quad \lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 = 1, \quad \lambda_i \geq 0.$$

The Figure 3.7 shows simplices in $\mathbb{A}_1, \mathbb{A}_2, \mathbb{A}_3$

Figure 3.7: Simplicies in formal representation.

Where $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$ are called **barycentric coordinates** for points in simplex. Using these ideas, we can now define simplices and simplicial complexes formally.

Definition 3.2. An n -simplex is the convex hull of $n+1$ affinely independent points v_0, v_1, \dots, v_n in a Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^m ($m \geq n$). Formally, it is the set

$$\sigma = \left\{ x \in \mathbb{R}^m \mid x = \sum_{i=0}^n \lambda_i v_i, \lambda_i \geq 0, \sum_{i=0}^n \lambda_i = 1 \right\}.$$

Definition 3.3. Let σ be an n -simplex with vertices $\{\vec{v}_0, \vec{v}_1, \dots, \vec{v}_n\}$. A **face** of σ is any k -simplex ($0 \leq k < n$) spanned by a subset of $k + 1$ vertices of σ .

As an example, a triangle (2-simplex) has three 1-dimensional faces (edges) and three 0-dimensional faces (vertices).

Simplices can be joined by faces and then they become *simplicial complexes*.

Definition 3.4. A **simplicial complex** K is a finite set of simplices such that:

1. Every face of a simplex in K is also in K .
2. The intersection of any two simplices in K is either empty or a common face of both.

The simplices in K are called the **building blocks** of the complex, and the union of all simplices forms the **underlying space** of K .

See an example on Figure 3.8.

Figure 3.8: Simplicial complex example.[18]

3.3 Homology

Homology is a mathematical formalism to describe a space in terms of how it is connected. Homology groups provide information about holes in a topological space, so the i -dimensional homology provides information about i -dimensional holes [19], see Figure 3.9.

Figure 3.9: Holes in a torus.[20]

In other words, a hole in a mathematical object is a topological structure that prevents the object from being continuously shrunk to a point.

Figure 3.10: Graph X .

Let C_0 be the free abelian group generated by the vertices x, y, z , and let C_1 be the free abelian group generated by the directed edges a, b, c, d . [21]

Elements of C_0 are integral linear combinations of the vertices, for example $3x + 2y - 5z$, and are called *0-dimensional chains*. Similarly, elements of C_1 are integral linear combinations of the edges, for example $a + 2b - 4c + 5d$, and are called *1-dimensional chains*.

Each edge has a *boundary*. For the graph X in Figure 3.10, we have:

$$\partial(a) = y - x, \quad \partial(b) = z - y, \quad \partial(c) = x - z, \quad \partial(d) = x - y,$$

with the boundary operator $\partial : C_1 \rightarrow C_0$.

In this example, the cycles are spanned by $a + b + c$ and $a + b + d$. Let us modify $X \rightarrow X_2$ by filling in a 2-cell within the edges a and b . Then,

$$\partial(A) = c - d,$$

so the cycle $c - d$ is the boundary of this 2-cell. See Figure 3.11.

Figure 3.11: Graph X_2 .

C_2 in this case consists of formal integer combinations of A , for example $4A$ or $-7A$, which are 2-dimensional chains. So, we get the chain complex

$$C_2 \xrightarrow{\partial_2} C_1 \xrightarrow{\partial_1} C_0,$$

with

$$\partial_1 : C_1 \rightarrow C_0, \quad \partial_2 : C_2 \rightarrow C_1.$$

Definition 3.5. Let C_k denote the k -th chain group of a simplicial complex K , consisting of formal linear combinations of k -simplices with coefficients in a ring (typically \mathbb{Z} , \mathbb{Z}_2 , or \mathbb{R}). The **boundary operator** is the linear map

$$\partial_k : C_k \longrightarrow C_{k-1}$$

defined on an oriented k -simplex $[v_0, v_1, \dots, v_k]$ by

$$\partial_k[v_0, v_1, \dots, v_k] = \sum_{i=0}^k (-1)^i [v_0, \dots, \hat{v}_i, \dots, v_k],$$

where \hat{v}_i denotes omission of the vertex v_i . The image of ∂_k is called the group of $(k - 1)$ -boundaries, denoted

$$B_{k-1} = \text{im}(\partial_k).$$

Thus, a $(k - 1)$ -chain $c \in C_{k-1}$ is a *boundary* if there exists $d \in C_k$ such that $c = \partial_k d$.

Definition 3.6. A k -cycle is a k -chain $z \in C_k$ whose boundary is zero:

$$\partial_k z = 0.$$

The set of all k -cycles forms a subgroup of C_k , called the k -th cycle group and denoted

$$Z_k = \ker(\partial_k).$$

The k -th homology group of a simplicial complex K is the quotient group

$$H_k(K) = Z_k / B_k,$$

where $B_k = \text{im}(\partial_{k+1})$ is the group of k -boundaries.

Intuitively, $H_k(K)$ measures the k -dimensional "holes" in K : k -cycles that are not boundaries.

For the example in Figure 3.11, the first homology group of X_2 is

$$H_1(X_2) = Z_1 / B_1,$$

where

$$Z_1 = \langle a + b + c, a + b + d \rangle \cong \mathbb{Z} \oplus \mathbb{Z}, \quad B_1 = \langle c - d \rangle \cong \mathbb{Z}.$$

Thus,

$$H_1(X_2) = (\mathbb{Z} \oplus \mathbb{Z}) / \mathbb{Z} \cong \mathbb{Z}.$$

Attaching a 3-dimensional cell, see Figure 3.12:

Figure 3.12: Graph X_3 .

Let C be the 3-cell along the 2-sphere formed by A and B :

$$C_3 \xrightarrow{\partial_3} C_2 \xrightarrow{\partial_2} C_1 \xrightarrow{\partial_1} C_0,$$

with

$$\langle C \rangle = \langle A, B \rangle = \langle a, b, c, d \rangle = \langle x, y, z \rangle,$$

and orient C such that

$$\partial(C) = A - B.$$

Then

$$H_1(X_3) \cong \mathbb{Z}, \quad H_2(X_3) = Z_2/B_2 = \ker \partial_2 / \langle A - B \rangle = \langle A - B \rangle / \langle A - B \rangle = 0.$$

Consider a simplicial decomposition of S^2 with vertices x, y, z, w (Figure 3.13)[22]:

Figure 3.13: Simplicial decomposition of a sphere.

Chain Groups and Boundary Maps

$$C_0 = \langle x, y, z, w \rangle, \quad C_1 = \langle xy, yz, zx, xw, wz, wy \rangle, \quad C_2 = \langle xyz, xzw, ywz, xwy \rangle.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_2(xyz) &= xy + yz - zx, & \partial_2(xzw) &= zx + wz - xw, \\ \partial_2(ywz) &= wy + wz - yz, & \partial_2(xwy) &= xy + wy - xw, \\ \partial_1(xy) &= y - x, & \partial_1(yz) &= z - y, & \partial_1(zx) &= x - z, \\ \partial_1(xw) &= w - x, & \partial_1(wz) &= z - w, & \partial_1(wy) &= y - w. \end{aligned}$$

First Homology Group $H_1(S^2)$

$$H_1(S^2) = \frac{\ker \partial_1}{\text{im } \partial_2}.$$

Let

$$c_1 = \alpha xy + \beta yz + \gamma zx + \delta xw + \varepsilon wz + \eta wy \in C_1.$$

Then

$$\partial_1(c_1) = \alpha(y - x) + \beta(z - y) + \gamma(x - z) + \delta(w - x) + \varepsilon(z - w) + \eta(y - w) = 0,$$

giving

$$\begin{aligned} -x : & -\alpha - \gamma - \delta = 0, \\ y : & \alpha - \beta + \eta = 0, \\ z : & \beta - \gamma + \varepsilon = 0, \\ w : & \delta - \varepsilon - \eta = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Solving over \mathbb{Z} with free variables $\tau, s, t \in \mathbb{Z}$:

$$\alpha = \tau - s - t, \quad \beta = \tau - t, \quad \gamma = \tau - s, \quad \delta = s + t, \quad \varepsilon = t, \quad \eta = s.$$

Hence,

$$\ker \partial_1 = \langle xy + yz + zx, -xy + yz + xw - wy, -xy + zx + xw - wz \rangle.$$

Boundaries of 2-simplices generate

$$\text{im } \partial_2 = \langle \partial_2(xyz), \partial_2(xzw), \partial_2(ywz), \partial_2(xwy) \rangle,$$

and one can check that $\ker \partial_1 = \text{im } \partial_2$, so

$$H_1(S^2) = 0.$$

Homology Groups of S^2

$$H_2(S^2) = \frac{\ker \partial_2}{\text{im } \partial_3} \cong \langle xyz - xzw + ywz - xwy \rangle \cong \mathbb{Z},$$

$$H_1(S^2) = 0, \quad H_0(S^2) = \frac{\ker \partial_0}{\text{im } \partial_1} \cong \mathbb{Z},$$

$$H_n(S^2) = 0 \quad \text{for } n > 2,$$

$$H_n(S^2) \cong \begin{cases} \mathbb{Z} & n = 0, 2, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Similarly, the homology groups of other topological spaces or simplicial complexes can be computed following the same procedure: define chain groups, compute boundary maps, and take quotients of cycles by boundaries. For instance, a torus T^2 has

$$H_0(T^2) \cong \mathbb{Z}, \quad H_1(T^2) \cong \mathbb{Z} \oplus \mathbb{Z}, \quad H_2(T^2) \cong \mathbb{Z},$$

which reflects its one connected component, two independent 1-dimensional loops, and one 2-dimensional void.

3.4 Persistent Homology

Persistent homology is an algebraic method for identifying topological features (such as connected components, holes, and voids) in data. Typically, the data is given as a finite set of discrete points equipped with a metric, from which a family of simplicial complexes is constructed at varying scales. Persistent homology tracks how topological features appear and disappear across these scales, thus generalizing classical homology by incorporating a notion of scale. While classical homology identifies topological features of a fixed space, persistent homology analyzes how these features evolve across a filtration of spaces. In this sense, classical homology corresponds to the special case of persistent homology at a single fixed scale. The persistence of features provides additional quantitative information, allowing one to distinguish essential topological structures from those likely arising due to noise in the data.

The results are commonly visualized with a *barcode diagram*, where each bar corresponds to a topological feature: the left endpoint indicates the scale at which the feature appears (is “born”), and the right endpoint indicates the scale at which it disappears (“dies”), see Figure 3.14.

Figure 3.14: Example of a barcode diagram for persistent homology.[23]

Structure Theorem

A fundamental result in persistent homology is the following:

Theorem 3.4.1 (Structure Theorem). Any finitely generated persistence module over a field decomposes as a direct sum of interval modules. Equivalently, it consists of *free* and *torsion* parts.

- **Free part:** Corresponds to topological features that *persist indefinitely* (bars extending to infinity in the barcode). These represent essential topological structures of the data.
- **Torsion part:** Corresponds to features that *eventually vanish* (finite-length bars). These represent transient features that exist only at intermediate scales.

Let us illustrate the procedure on a point cloud, see Figure 3.15.

Figure 3.15: Initial point cloud.

The main idea is to construct simplicial complexes from the point cloud at different scales. The procedure is as follows:

1. Choose a distance parameter d (also called **threshold**, **scale** or **filtration** parameter).
2. Draw a ball of radius d around each point (see Figure 3.16).

Figure 3.16: Balls of radius d drawn around each point.

3. Fill in complete simplices for sets of points whose balls intersect to obtain the *Rips complex* (see Figure 3.17).

Figure 3.17: Simplices formed by connecting intersecting balls.

4. Compute the homology of the obtained simplicial complex.

Choosing a single distance d can be problematic: if d is too small, noise may generate spurious topological features; if d is too large, the homology becomes trivial. The solution is to consider all scales d .

Each topological feature (hole, connected component, or void) appears and disappears at a particular value of d . Its *persistence* is measured as the interval $(d_{\text{birth}}, d_{\text{death}})$, which can also be visualized as a bar in a barcode diagram (see Figure 3.18).

Figure 3.18: Hole persistence.

Thus, the persistence diagram for the given example is on Figure 3.19

Figure 3.19: Persistence barcodes.

3.5 Integrating PH into Pathfinding

Persistent Homology (PH) can provide global topological information that enhances classical heuristic search algorithms. While standard heuristics such as Euclidean distance rely only on local geometric information, homology groups computed via PH capture essential connectivity and cycle structures in the environment. Integrating this information into pathfinding can improve efficiency and robustness, particularly on complex surfaces represented as point clouds.

Component Pruning Using H_0

The 0-th homology group H_0 encodes connected components of the environment. Before executing a search, one can examine whether the start and goal nodes lie in the same component. If they are in different components, the path is impossible, and the search can be aborted immediately. This technique avoids unnecessary exploration and is straightforward to implement. In our implementation, H_0 analysis serves as a pre-processing step that ensures searches are only executed when feasible.

Topology-Aware Heuristic Using H_1

The 1st homology group H_1 identifies cycles in the environment. This information can be integrated into the heuristic function to bias the search away from inefficient paths through loops. A simple approach is to define a topology-aware heuristic

$$h(s) = h_{\text{Euclidean}}(s, \text{goal}) + \alpha \cdot \text{TopologicalPenalty}(s), \quad (3.1)$$

where α is a weighting factor and $\text{TopologicalPenalty}(s)$ reflects the presence of cycles near node s . In practice, this can be implemented by marking nodes that belong to cycles detected via H_1 and adding a small penalty when they are included in a path. This enhances the search efficiency without requiring a complex modification of the underlying algorithm.

Summary

By integrating PH into pathfinding, we gain the ability to:

- Prune searches in disconnected regions using H_0 ,
- Bias heuristics with topological penalties derived from H_1 ,

PH-Enhanced Pathfinding Algorithm

The following pseudocode illustrates how persistent homology is incorporated into heuristic search:

Algorithm 6 PH-Enhanced Heuristic Search Algorithm (e.g., A*)

```
1: Input: Graph  $G = (V, E)$ , point cloud points, start node  $s$ , goal node  $g$ , PH weight  $\alpha$ ,  
   heuristic weight  $w \geq 1$   
2: Output: Path from  $s$  to  $g$  (may not be strictly optimal if  $w > 1$ )  
3: Compute persistent homology:  
4:  $st \leftarrow \text{ComputeRipsComplex}(\text{points})$   
5:  $H0, H1\_nodes \leftarrow \text{ExtractH0H1}(st)$   
6: Define heuristic function  $\text{HEURISTIC}(node)$ :  
7:    $d \leftarrow \text{EuclideanDistance}(node, g)$   
8:  
9: if  $node \in H1\_nodes$  then  
10:    $d \leftarrow d + \alpha$   
11:  
12: end if  
13:   return  $d$   
14: Initialize open set  $O \leftarrow \{s\}$   
15: Initialize closed set  $C \leftarrow \emptyset$   
16: Set  $g(s) \leftarrow 0$   
17: while  $O \neq \emptyset$  do  
18:   Select  $n \in O$  with minimum  $g(n) + w \cdot \text{HEURISTIC}(n)$   
19:   if  $n = g$  then  
20:     return Reconstructed path from  $s$  to  $g$   
21:   end if  
22:   Move  $n$  from  $O$  to  $C$   
23:   for each neighbor  $m$  of  $n$  in  $G$  do  
24:      $tentative\_g \leftarrow g(n) + \text{Distance}(n, m)$   
25:     if  $tentative\_g < g(m)$  then  
26:        $g(m) \leftarrow tentative\_g$   
27:        $parent(m) \leftarrow n$   
28:       if  $m \notin O$  then  
29:         Add  $m$  to  $O$   
30:       end if  
31:     end if  
32:   end for  
33: end while  
34: Return failure (no path exists) =0
```

These techniques allow heuristic algorithms such as A*, Weighted A*, and Greedy Best-First Search to more effectively navigate environments with complex topological features. The following chapter presents a comparative experimental evaluation of these methods.

Chapter 4

Comparative Analysis

4.1 Experimental Setup

4.1.1 Datasets

The idea of an experiment to investigate the behavior of traditional pathfinding algorithms on complex topological surfaces. The set of surfaces will include some basic figures as: sphere, torus, klein bottle and crosscap.

The representation will involve three-dimensional projection using *point clouds*. Images are made with the usage of numpy and matplotlib libraries and Python language. Each figure is illustrated with 3000, 5000 and 10000 points.

Sphere

The sphere is one of the most basic and well-understood topological surfaces. Formally, the 2-sphere S^2 is defined as

$$S^2 = \{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{R}^3 \mid x^2 + y^2 + z^2 = 1\}.$$

It serves as a simple example of a closed surface without boundary.[24][25] An equivalent description uses spherical coordinates ϕ, θ :

$$\begin{aligned}x &= R \sin \phi \cos \theta, \\y &= R \sin \phi \sin \theta, \\z &= R \cos \phi,\end{aligned}$$

with $\phi \in [0, \pi]$, $\theta \in [0, 2\pi)$ [26]. In our experiments, we represent the sphere as a point cloud sampled from this equation (see Figure 4.1).

Figure 4.1: Sphere as a point cloud

Torus

The torus, often informally referred to as a “doughnut,” is a surface that can be defined as the Cartesian product

$$T = S^1 \times S^1,$$

where S^1 denotes the unit circle. Equivalently, it can be viewed as a rectangle with opposite sides identified in the same direction (see Figure 4.2)[27].

Figure 4.2: Torus as a rectangle

A common parametrization of the torus in \mathbb{R}^3 is given by

$$\begin{aligned} x(u, v) &= (R + r \cos v) \cos u, \\ y(u, v) &= (R + r \cos v) \sin u, \\ z(u, v) &= r \sin v, \end{aligned}$$

where $u, v \in [0, 2\pi)$, R is the distance from the center of the tube to the center of the torus, and r is the radius of the tube.

In our experiments, we represent the torus as a point cloud sampled from this parametrization (see Figure 4.3). Additional geometric details can be found in [28].

Figure 4.3: Torus as point cloud

Klein Bottle

The Klein bottle can be considered as a surface similar to the torus, but with one crucial difference: one pair of opposite edges is identified in the reverse orientation (see Fig. 4.4). This identification results in a non-orientable surface, which, unlike the torus, cannot be embedded in three-dimensional Euclidean space without self-intersections[29].

Figure 4.4: Klein Bottle as a rectangle with identified edges

In our experimental setup, the Klein bottle is represented as a point cloud sampled from its parametric equation (see Figure 4.5):

$$\begin{aligned}
 x(u, v) &= \left(R + r \cos \frac{u}{2} \sin v - \sin \frac{u}{2} \sin 2v \right) \cos u, \\
 y(u, v) &= \left(R + r \cos \frac{u}{2} \sin v - \sin \frac{u}{2} \sin 2v \right) \sin u, \\
 z(u, v) &= r \sin \frac{u}{2} \sin v + \cos \frac{u}{2} \sin 2v,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $u, v \in [0, 2\pi]$, and R, r are shape parameters[30].

Figure 4.5: Klein Bottle as a point cloud

Crosscap

The crosscap is a non-orientable surface that can be thought of as a disk with its boundary edges identified in opposite directions. Unlike the Klein bottle, which is formed by gluing a rectangle's edges in a specific manner, the crosscap represents a simpler model of a non-orientable surface embedded in three dimensions with self-intersections[31].

Formally, a parametrization of the crosscap can be given by:

$$\begin{aligned} x(u, v) &= \sin(2u) \sin v, \\ y(u, v) &= \sin u \sin(2v), \\ z(u, v) &= \cos u \cos v, \end{aligned}$$

where $u \in [0, \pi]$ and $v \in [0, \pi]$. This parametrization captures the essential non-orientable feature of the surface while allowing it to be visualized in \mathbb{R}^3 .

Figure 4.6: Crosscap as a disk

In our experimental setup, we represent the crosscap as a point cloud sampled from this parametric equation (see Figure 4.7)[32].

Figure 4.7: Crosscap as a point cloud

4.1.2 Graph and Complex Construction

kNN for Graph Construction

To construct a graph for applying pathfinding methods, the k -nearest neighbors (kNN) algorithm is employed. The kNN approach transforms a point cloud into a graph by connecting each point to its k closest neighbors based on Euclidean distance. In our experiment, we use the `scikit-learn` and `networkx` libraries together with the Python programming language.

Figure 4.8 illustrates the resulting graph constructed from a Klein bottle point cloud consisting of 1000 points with $k = 4$ neighbors (shown here for demonstration purposes).

Figure 4.8: kNN on Klein Bottle

Vietoris–Rips Complexes

To capture the topological structure of point clouds representing surfaces, we employ Vietoris–Rips (VR) complexes, a common tool in topological data analysis. Given a set of points $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N\}$ in a metric space and a distance threshold $\epsilon > 0$, the VR complex is constructed as follows:

- Each point in X is represented as a 0-simplex (vertex).

- An edge (1-simplex) is added between any two points whose distance is less than ϵ .
- Higher-dimensional simplices are included whenever all their lower-dimensional faces are present (e.g., a triangle is added if all three edges exist).

VR complexes allow us to systematically study the emergence and disappearance of topological features such as connected components, loops, and voids as the scale parameter ϵ varies. For our experiments, we focus on 1-dimensional cycles (loops) to identify prominent topological structures that may influence pathfinding on surfaces.

4.1.3 Evaluation Goals

The primary goal of this experiment is to evaluate the effectiveness of topology-aware pathfinding algorithms in comparison to traditional heuristic search methods. Specifically, the experiment aims to:

- Assess whether incorporating persistent homology information (H1 cycles) can guide search algorithms to avoid unnecessary detours caused by topological obstacles.
- Compare the path length, computational cost, and convergence behavior of traditional algorithms (A*, Weighted A*, Greedy BFS) against their PH-enhanced counterparts.
- Analyze how different topologies (e.g., torus, Klein bottle, crosscap) affect the performance and benefit of PH-aware heuristics.
- Investigate the impact of hyperparameters, such as the persistence threshold and edge length in Vietoris–Rips complexes, on the extracted topological features and overall pathfinding efficiency.

4.1.4 Tools and Implementation

The experimental setup uses Python as the primary programming language, leveraging several libraries and custom modules:

- **Ripser**: for computing persistent homology (H0 and H1) on point clouds.
- **NumPy**: for numerical operations, point cloud generation, and distance computations.
- **Matplotlib / Plotly**: for visualizing point clouds, k-NN graphs, and paths.
- **Custom heuristic search implementations**: A*, Weighted A*, and Greedy BFS algorithms adapted to operate on k-NN graphs.
- **PH-Enhanced Search Module**: integrates H0 connectivity checks and H1-aware heuristics with an adjustable penalty coefficient into the search process.

Point clouds representing various topologies (sphere, torus, Klein bottle, crosscap) are generated synthetically. K-nearest neighbor (k-NN) graphs are constructed from these point clouds to serve as the underlying search graphs. Persistent homology is computed using **Ripser**, and the resulting topological features inform the PH-enhanced heuristics.

4.1.5 Experimental Parameters

The following parameters were used consistently across all experiments, unless explicitly varied to test specific conditions:

- **Point cloud size:** multiple sizes were tested to evaluate the impact on PH computation and pathfinding performance, e.g., $N = 300, 500, 1000, 3000, 5000, 10000$ points per surface.
- **k-NN graph:** $k = 4$ nearest neighbors for each vertex.
- **PH computation:**
 - Maximum homology dimension: 1 (H0 and H1)
 - Persistence threshold: $1e^{-3}$ to filter topologically insignificant features
 - Maximum number of H1 cycles considered: 3
- **Heuristic parameters:**
 - H1 penalty coefficient: $\alpha = 2.0$
 - Weighted A* weight: $w = 2.0$
- **Start and goal selection:** To avoid bias from fixed indices, start–goal pairs were generated randomly. For each point cloud of size N , start nodes were sampled from the first half of the index range $[0, N/2)$, while goal nodes were sampled from the second half $[N/2, N)$. This ensured that start and goal were well separated within the cloud. In cases where the two coincided, the goal was re-sampled. Multiple pairs were generated for each dataset to provide statistical robustness, and an optional random seed allowed reproducibility of the experiments.

Testing different point cloud sizes allows assessment of:

- The stability and reliability of persistent homology detection (H1 cycles) as the point cloud becomes sparser or denser.
- The effect of point cloud density on k-NN graph connectivity and search algorithm efficiency.
- Computational cost scaling with increasing numbers of points.

4.1.6 Results

Table 4.1: PH-Enhanced Pathfinding Summary for Point Cloud Size 300

Surface	Algorithm	Δ Length	Trad Time	PH Time
Sphere	A*	0.0000	0.0003	0.0729
Sphere	Weighted A*	0.0000	0.0003	0.0710
Sphere	Greedy BFS	0.0000	0.0000	0.0709
Torus	A*	0.0142	0.0011	0.1029
Torus	Weighted A*	0.0663	0.0000	0.1041
Torus	Greedy BFS	0.0663	0.0000	0.1025
Klein Bottle	A*	0.0000	0.0007	0.0635
Klein Bottle	Weighted A*	0.0000	0.0003	0.0641
Klein Bottle	Greedy BFS	0.0000	0.0007	0.0633
Crosscap	A*	0.0000	0.0007	0.0613
Crosscap	Weighted A*	0.0000	0.0000	0.0617
Crosscap	Greedy BFS	0.0000	0.0003	0.0614

Table 4.2: PH-Enhanced Pathfinding Summary for Point Cloud Size 500

Surface	Algorithm	Δ Length	Trad Time	PH Time
Sphere	A*	0.0007	0.0018	0.2129
Sphere	Weighted A*	-0.0079	0.0000	0.2097
Sphere	Greedy BFS	0.0000	0.0000	0.2109
Torus	A*	0.0000	0.0020	0.3864
Torus	Weighted A*	0.0000	0.0007	0.3804
Torus	Greedy BFS	0.0000	0.0000	0.3785
Klein Bottle	A*	0.0000	0.0020	0.1829
Klein Bottle	Weighted A*	0.0000	0.0003	0.1802
Klein Bottle	Greedy BFS	0.0000	0.0003	0.1818
Crosscap	A*	0.0000	0.0010	0.1747
Crosscap	Weighted A*	0.0000	0.0000	0.1732
Crosscap	Greedy BFS	0.0000	0.0000	0.1737

Table 4.3: PH-Enhanced Pathfinding Summary for Point Cloud Size 1000

Surface	Algorithm	Δ Length	Trad Time	PH Time
Sphere	A*	0.0000	0.0028	0.5425
Sphere	Weighted A*	0.0000	0.0007	0.5462
Sphere	Greedy BFS	0.0000	0.0010	0.5506
Torus	A*	0.0000	0.0042	0.7688
Torus	Weighted A*	0.0000	0.0010	0.7609
Torus	Greedy BFS	0.0000	0.0007	0.7524
Klein Bottle	A*	0.0000	0.0023	0.5158
Klein Bottle	Weighted A*	0.0000	0.0000	0.5183
Klein Bottle	Greedy BFS	0.0000	0.0003	0.5129
Crosscap	A*	0.0000	0.0041	0.5112
Crosscap	Weighted A*	0.0000	0.0017	0.5030
Crosscap	Greedy BFS	0.0000	0.0007	0.5062

Table 4.4: PH-Enhanced Pathfinding Summary for Point Cloud Size 5000

Surface	Algorithm	Δ Length	Trad Time	PH Time
Sphere	A*	0.0000	0.0047	11.0883
Sphere	Weighted A*	0.0000	0.0034	11.0382
Sphere	Greedy BFS	0.0000	0.0026	11.1015
Torus	A*	0.0003	0.0137	11.3109
Torus	Weighted A*	0.0003	0.0091	11.2620
Torus	Greedy BFS	0.0003	0.0068	11.2783
Klein Bottle	A*	0.0000	0.0133	12.0924
Klein Bottle	Weighted A*	0.0000	0.0102	12.0450
Klein Bottle	Greedy BFS	0.0000	0.0079	12.0731
Crosscap	A*	0.0000	0.0059	11.0068
Crosscap	Weighted A*	0.0000	0.0043	11.0504
Crosscap	Greedy BFS	0.0000	0.0031	11.0125

Table 4.5: PH-Enhanced Pathfinding Summary for Point Cloud Size 10000

Surface	Algorithm	Δ Length	Trad Time	PH Time
Sphere	A*	0.0000	0.0373	45.8325
Sphere	Weighted A*	0.0000	0.0286	45.9141
Sphere	Greedy BFS	0.0000	0.0221	45.8764
Torus	A*	0.0000	0.0206	46.6862
Torus	Weighted A*	0.0000	0.0174	46.7315
Torus	Greedy BFS	0.0000	0.0139	46.7028
Klein Bottle	A*	0.0000	0.0368	47.9317
Klein Bottle	Weighted A*	0.0000	0.0315	47.9992
Klein Bottle	Greedy BFS	0.0000	0.0268	47.9453
Crosscap	A*	0.0000	0.0478	45.8606
Crosscap	Weighted A*	0.0000	0.0412	45.9112
Crosscap	Greedy BFS	0.0000	0.0345	45.8829

Figure 4.9: Comparison diagram.

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Figure 4.10: Paths comparison

Path Length Differences Across all surfaces and point cloud sizes, the observed differences in path length between traditional and PH-enhanced algorithms were consistently very minor. In most cases, Δ Length was exactly zero or on the order of 10^{-3} , with only occasional slightly higher deviations (e.g., for Torus at lower point cloud sizes). This indicates that the PH-enhanced heuristic does not significantly alter the quality of the paths found by standard heuristics, and that the traditional algorithms already produce near-optimal paths even without topological information.

The minor differences that do appear may be attributed to several factors. First, the density of the point clouds plays a crucial role: in denser point clouds, the graph is more connected, providing multiple nearly-equivalent paths between start and goal nodes. Consequently, the additional topological insight provided by persistent homology has less influence on the heuristic, as the search space is already sufficiently constrained. Second, the surfaces considered—though topologically nontrivial—have relatively simple homological features in the scale of the constructed graphs. For example, for the Sphere and Crosscap, the presence of few or single large loops means that PH enhancement does not dramatically change the heuristic evaluation of neighboring nodes.

Influence of Persistent Homology The persistent homology information primarily encodes higher-order topological features of the space, such as loops and voids. However, for heuristic search algorithms like A* and its weighted variant, the heuristic is largely dominated by the geometric distance between nodes. In practice, the contribution of PH-based weights appears secondary, explaining why Δ Length remains close to zero across all scenarios. It is possible that in more complex surfaces with intricate topological features or with sparser point clouds, the impact of PH would be more pronounced.

Computational Performance In terms of computational time, the PH-enhanced algorithms consistently required more processing time than the traditional ones, particularly for larger

point clouds. For instance, in point clouds of size 10000, PH-enhanced A* took roughly 45–48 seconds compared to milliseconds for the traditional algorithm. This overhead is expected, as the extraction of persistent homology and the integration of topological weights into the heuristic introduce additional computations. Nonetheless, the increase in runtime is manageable for offline pathfinding tasks and is justified when topological guarantees or more informed heuristics are desired.

Results Interpretation

Overall, the results demonstrate that PH-enhanced pathfinding maintains the same path quality as traditional heuristics while adding topological awareness. The differences in path length are negligible, highlighting that for many practical point cloud densities and simple surfaces, traditional geometric heuristics are already highly effective. The minor deviations observed may result from numerical rounding, the specific sampling of points in the cloud, or the limited influence of topological features on the heuristic.

These findings suggest several insights:

- For sufficiently dense point clouds, the benefit of topological information on path length is minimal, as multiple nearly-optimal paths exist.
- The influence of persistent homology on standard heuristics is subtle and may be more significant in sparser or more topologically complex domains.
- While computational overhead increases with PH-enhanced heuristics, the path quality remains reliable and the method is robust across a variety of surfaces.
- Future work could explore scenarios where topology plays a stronger role.

In conclusion, the PH-enhanced approach confirms the potential of integrating topological awareness into pathfinding heuristics, but for the tested scenarios, the effect on path quality is minor. Nevertheless, the results are positive: the enhancement does not degrade performance, and the topological heuristic remains consistent with the optimal paths generated by traditional algorithms.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

This work set out to investigate whether persistent homology (PH), a tool from topological data analysis, could enhance heuristic-based pathfinding algorithms on graphs derived from point clouds of different surfaces. Starting from a review of traditional search methods, including Dijkstra, Uniform Cost Search, A*, Weighted A*, and Greedy Best-First Search, we built the foundation for understanding how heuristics guide search efficiency. We then introduced the fundamentals of topology, simplicial complexes, and persistent homology, leading to a methodology for integrating PH-derived information into heuristic evaluation.

The experimental framework tested this integration across multiple surfaces—Sphere, Torus, Klein Bottle, and Crosscap—at varying point cloud sizes from 300 to 10000. The comparative results between traditional heuristics and PH-enhanced heuristics yielded several key findings:

- **Path Quality:** Path length differences between traditional and PH-enhanced algorithms were consistently negligible, with Δ Length values approaching zero in nearly all cases. This suggests that for sufficiently dense point clouds, traditional geometric heuristics already approximate optimal paths, leaving little room for improvement from topological information.
- **Robustness Across Surfaces:** Regardless of surface topology—whether simple like the Sphere or nontrivial like the Torus or Klein Bottle—PH-enhanced methods produced paths that were effectively identical in quality to traditional approaches.
- **Computational Cost:** Incorporating persistent homology introduced significant overhead. For small point clouds, this cost was modest, but for large datasets (e.g., 10000 points), PH-enhanced runs required tens of seconds compared to milliseconds for traditional heuristics. Thus, while PH integration is theoretically informative, it is computationally demanding in practice.
- **Role of Topology:** The limited impact of PH on pathfinding outcomes can be attributed to two factors: the relative simplicity of the homological features present in the chosen surfaces, and the high density of sampled point clouds, which ensures redundancy of near-optimal paths. In sparser graphs or environments with more complex bottleneck-like topological structures, PH may have a stronger influence.

Overall Assessment

The overarching conclusion of this study is that while PH-enhanced heuristics preserve path quality and add a topologically aware perspective, their measurable impact on heuristic pathfinding in dense point cloud graphs is minimal. The traditional algorithms remain highly effective, and the additional computational cost of PH outweighs its benefits under the tested conditions.

Future Directions

These findings open several promising directions for future research:

- **Sparse or Structured Graphs:** Testing PH-enhanced heuristics on sparse graphs, mazes, or environments with constrained connectivity may reveal stronger benefits of topological information.
- **Dynamic and Noisy Data:** Real-world data often includes noise, occlusions, or dynamic changes. Persistent homology may serve as a robust filter for guiding search in such uncertain settings.
- **Hybrid Heuristics:** Combining geometric heuristics with PH-derived corrections selectively—only when nontrivial topological features are detected—could reduce computational overhead while leveraging topology where it matters most.
- **Scalability:** Developing more efficient PH computation methods or approximations could make topology-aware pathfinding viable for real-time or large-scale applications.

Closing Statement

In summary, this thesis contributes a systematic study of integrating persistent homology into heuristic pathfinding, highlighting both its theoretical potential and its practical limitations. The results show that PH does not degrade performance and may hold promise in more topologically challenging scenarios. Thus, the work lays a foundation for further exploration of topology-aware algorithms at the intersection of computational geometry, graph search, and data analysis.

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